

Studies of Vitamin B₁. Part I. Synthesis of Some Analogues of Thiamine

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Synthesis of some analogues of thiamine hydrochloride viz., 2'-ethyl-, 2'-propyl^{1a}-, 2'-butyl^{1b}-, 2'-phenyl-, and 2'-benzyl-thiamine is described.

In connection with our study on the cocarboxylase activity of vitamin B₁, some analogues of the vitamin with substituents of higher alkyl or aryl groups at 2-position and a substituted amino group at 4-position of the pyrimidine moiety of the vitamin were required. These analogues are generally prepared by the methods of Williams and Cline¹ and Corewe² and are used for the synthesis of thiamine, but the method of Andersage and Westphal³ has not been used for their preparation so far. We have used this method³ with slight modification for the preparation of 2'-ethyl-, 2'-propyl^{1a}-, 2'-butyl^{1b}-, 2'-phenyl-, 2'-benzyl-thiamines.

Formyl ethyl succinate was condensed with the corresponding alkyl or aryl amidines to furnish ethyl 2'-alkyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-pyrimidine acetates. The latter on heating with phosphorus oxychloride in dry benzene afforded the corresponding 4-chloro compound which on reaction with ammonia under pressure furnished a good yield of 2'-alkyl-4'-amino-5'-pyrimidylacetamides. Hoffman's degradation of the latter and subsequent conversion of the aminomethyl group, thus formed, into 4'-bromomethyl via the intermediate formation of the corresponding 4'-hydroxymethyl derivatives furnished a satisfactory yield of 2'-alkyl-4'-amino-5'-bromomethylpyrimidine hydrobromides. The latter compounds on condensation with the thiazole moiety of vitamin B₁ provided the desired analogues. In this way six 2'-alkylthiamines having the alkyl groups as Et, Prⁿ, Buⁿ, Ph, and benzyl have been prepared.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 2'-R-4'-Hydroxy-5'-pyrimidine Acetate

To a suspension of powdered sodium (4.8 g.) in sodium-dried benzene (100 ml) in a three-necked flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer, a separatory funnel, and a reflux condenser, protected by calcium chloride tube, was added dropwise at 0°-5° a mixture of diethyl succinate (36 g.) and ethyl formate (15 g.). After addition of about one third of the mixture, a brisk reaction started, turning the solution yellow. After total addition, the contents were stirred for 8 hours to complete the reaction and the flask was immersed in an ice bath and cooled to 2°.

A solution of the amidine hydrochloride (0.2M), prepared by the method of Pyman (R=Et, m.p. 128°; R=Prⁿ, m.p. 94-96°; R=Buⁿ, nitrate m.p. 138°; R=Ph, m.p. 74°;

1. J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1937, 59, 1052.
2. Z. physiol. Chem., 1935, 237, 98.
3. Ber., 1937, 70, 2035.

R=C₆H₅CH₂, nitrate m.p. 170°), in absolute ethanol was introduced into the flask through the separatory funnel. During the addition of amidine solution, the temperature of the flask was kept below 5°, after which it was allowed to come to room temperature and then heated on a water bath for 6 hours when the reaction was complete. The mixture was filtered hot and the solid cake of sodium chloride was washed twice with 100 ml-portion of absolute ethanol. The filtrates were combined; the volume was reduced to half and cooled in ice-bath when ethyl 2'-R-4'-hydroxy-5'-pyrimidine acetates separated as bright needles. These were crystallised from absolute ethanol (Table I).

TABLE I

2'-R.	M.P.	Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Et	186°	83.0%	57.05	57.14	6.00	6.80
Pr ⁿ	148-49°	59.7	58.60	58.92	7.39	7.14
Bu ⁿ	141°	52.4	60.30	60.67	7.35	7.56
Ph	170°	56.0	64.87	65.11	5.21	5.42
PhCH ₂	176°	60.0	60.23	66.17	5.61	5.88

Ethyl 2'-R-4'-Chloro-5'-pyrimidine Acetate

A solution of ethyl 2'-R-4'-hydroxy-5'-pyrimidine acetate (0.2M) in dry benzene (150 ml) was taken in a 500-ml r.b. flask and freshly distilled POCl₃ (0.2M) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hours and then the solvent removed under vacuum. The dark red residue was dissolved in benzene (100 ml) and poured on crushed ice (100 g.) with stirring. The mixture was neutralised with sodium carbonate, the benzene layer separated, and the aqueous layer was once extracted with benzene (30 ml). The combined extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed on a water bath and the residual liquid on distillation under vacuum furnished the desired product (Table II).

TABLE II

2'-R.	B.P.	Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Et	145-46°/6mm (m.p. 42°)	78.0%	52.06	52.51	5.84	5.61
Pr ⁿ	165°/25	60.6	53.96	54.43	6.18	6.18
Bu ⁿ	Used as such	84.0	56.14	56.32	6.62	6.40
Ph	182°/5-6	66.8	60.75	60.39	4.70	4.36
PhCH ₂	195-98°/5	72.0	61.98	62.13	5.16	4.83

2'-R-4'-Amino-5'-pyrimidine Acetamide

Ethyl 2'-R-4'-chloro-5'-pyrimidine acetate (0.1M) was dissolved in dry methanol (150 ml) containing 12-15% of ammonia and heated in a steel autoclave at 120-30° for 8 hours. The contents were transferred to an evaporating dish and excess of ammonia and methanol removed by boiling. The residue was dissolved in hot ethanol, treated with active charcoal, and filtered. The filtrate on concentration under vacuum and cooling furnished white crystals of 2'-R-4'-amino-5'-pyrimidine acetamides (Table III).

TABLE III

2'-R.	M.P.	Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Et	233-34°	88.2%	53.33	53.08	6.60	6.34
Pr ⁿ	215°	76.2	55.66	55.32	7.21	6.83
Bu ⁿ	242°	75.0	57.69	57.24	7.69	7.37
Ph	177°	68.0	63.15	63.46	5.26	5.02
PhCH ₃	238°	72.0	60.42	60.02	5.28	5.49

2'-R-4'-Amino-5'-aminomethylpyrimidines

Bromine (5 g.) was slowly added with stirring to 2.5*N*-KOH (60 ml) in a flask, kept surrounded with ice-salt freezing mixture. To this was added 4'-amino-5'-pyrimidine acetamide (7.5 g.), suspended in 5*N*-KOH solution and stirred. When the pyrimidine had dissolved, a further quantity of 50% KOH (20ml) was added slowly. After the reaction was over, the alkaline solution was extracted several times with ether; extracts were combined and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removing ether, the residue was dissolved in hot ethanol and treated with Norit and filtered. The ethanol was removed and the residue was dissolved in absolute ether; the solution was cooled in ice. On passing dry HCl, a white flocculent mass of 2'-R-4'-amino-5'-aminomethylpyrimidine-2HCl separated. It was filtered, washed with anhydrous ether, and dried (solid NaOH).

In another process, the diamine was isolated as dibenzaldine derivative by addition of a requisite amount of benzaldehyde. The solid mass was decomposed with *N*-HCl and steam-distilled to remove benzaldehyde. The aqueous layer was evaporated to dryness under vacuum and the diamine dihydrochloride crystallised from ethanol (Table IV).

TABLE IV

2'-R-4'-Amino-5'-aminomethylpyrimidine dihydrochlorides.

2'-R.	M.P.	Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Et	229°	76%	36.93	37.33	5.84	6.22
Pr ⁿ	243°	68	40.35	40.16	5.62	5.85
Bu ⁿ	212°	65	42.27	42.68	5.25	5.83
Ph	291°	78	48.10	48.35	4.85	5.12
PhCH ₃	260°	58	49.70	50.16	5.11	5.57

2'-R-4'-Amino-5'-hydroxymethylpyrimidine

To a solution of 2'-R-4'-amino-5'-aminomethylpyrimidine dihydrochloride (0.05 g.) in water (100ml) was added dropwise at 50-60° a solution of sodium nitrite (0.05 g.) in water (30ml). After addition of water, the solution was stirred for 4 to 6 hours at the same temperature till evolution of nitrogen had ceased. The solution was cooled, neutralised with Na₂CO₃, and evaporated to dryness under vacuum. The white pulp was then extracted with boiling acetone; the extract was concentrated and cooled when the pyrimidine separated as a white mass. This was then converted into the hydrochloride by usual methods.

TABLE V

2'-R.	M.P.	Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Et	174°	58.5%	43.91	44.32	5.93	6.30
Pr ⁿ	169°	53.4	49.73	47.17	6.35	6.68
Bu ⁿ	196°	60.6	49.27	49.06	7.35	7.35
Ph	199°	62.4	55.17	55.58	4.85	5.05
PhCH ₂	214°	56.8	57.35	57.23	5.06	5.56

2'-R-4'-Amino-5'-bromomethylpyrimidine Hydrobromide

2'-R-4'-Amino-5'-hydroxymethylpyrimidine hydrochloride (0.1g. mol.) was heated on a water bath with 15-20% HBr in glacial acetic acid. During this period the hydroxypyrimidine derivative slowly went into solution and a microcrystalline substance began to separate. When the reaction was over (1 to 2 hours), the solution was cooled, filtered, and the residue washed well with dry ether. The product was dried in a vacuum desiccator.

TABLE VI

2'-R.	M.P.	Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Et	180°	76%	28.35	28.28	3.30	3.70
Pr ⁿ	232°	68	30.61	30.87	4.24	4.18
Bu ⁿ	167°	62	32.90	33.23	4.28	4.61
Ph	165°	72	38.02	38.25	3.22	3.20
PhCH ₂	196°	65	30.74	40.12	3.79	3.62

2'-R-Thiamines or 2'-R-4'-Amino-5'-(4-methyl-5-hydroxyethylthiazolium bromide)-methylpyrimidine Hydrobromide

4'-Amino-5'-bromomethylpyrimidine hydrobromide (2 g.) and a slight excess of the equivalent amount (1:1) of 4'-methyl-5'-hydroxyethylthiazole and butanolⁿ (2ml) were heated at 118-20° for 15 mins. During this period the bromo-pyrimidine went into solution and the vitamin began to separate. After cooling, ether was added until a permanent turbidity appeared. After this the solution was cooled in ice and filtered. The product was dissolved in hot ethanol and treated with a small amount of active charcoal and filtered. After cooling, ethyl acetate was added dropwise until turbidity appeared. The solution was then allowed to cool when yellowish white needles of the vitamins separated. These were filtered and washed with ether or acetone.

TABLE VII

2'-R.	M.P.*	Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Et	235°	52%	35.10	35.45	4.28	4.54	12.75	12.42
Pr ⁿ	244-45°	58	36.70	37.00	4.66	4.84	11.96	12.33
Bu ⁿ	228°	62	38.05	38.47	4.84	5.12	11.54	11.99
Ph	230°	57	41.67	41.60	3.77	4.80	11.21	11.47
PhCH ₂	225°	62	42.84	43.03	4.03	4.38	10.88	11.16

*With decomposition.

The effect of these compounds on the decarboxylation of pyruvic acid by alkali-washed yeast apoenzyme in presence of pure cocarboxylase and Mg²⁺ has been shown in a separate communication.